

SUSTAINABLE BIOETHANOL PRODUCTION FROM FOOD WASTE: A NOVEL ECO-FRIENDLY APPROACH USING POTATO PEELS

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Abstract

This study proposes a novel and eco-friendly method for producing high-quality bioethanol from potato peels, aimed at use as a gasoline blend base. The process begins with the collection, washing, and drying of potato peels, followed by acid hydrolysis to release and convert starch into fermentable sugars. These sugars are then subjected to fermentation using the microorganism *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, which efficiently converts them into bioethanol under carefully controlled conditions. Finally, the bioethanol is purified using rotary evaporation, a technique that ensures efficient ethanol recovery while minimizing thermal degradation. The use of rotary evaporation not only enhances the purity of the bioethanol but also reduces energy consumption compared to traditional distillation methods, yielding a product that meets both American and European quality standards. By optimizing each step of the process, from hydrolysis to fermentation and evaporation, this study demonstrates the feasibility of producing bioethanol that is both cost-effective and environmentally sustainable. A detailed analysis of the physicochemical properties of the resulting bioethanol—such as water content, purity, total acidity, and compliance with industry standards—validates the quality of bioethanol derived from potato peels. This approach not only highlights the potential of food waste as a valuable resource for renewable energy production but also supports a circular economy by transforming waste into a clean, sustainable fuel. The results of this study underscore the dual benefits of this method: providing a high-quality bioethanol suitable for blending with gasoline and reducing the environmental impact of food waste, paving the way for innovative solutions in the field of biofuels.

Index Terms: Bioethanol, Potato Peels, Renewable Energy, Gasoline Blend Base, Waste Valorization, Sustainable Biofuels, Environmental Impact Reduction.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the face of escalating environmental challenges and rising global energy demand, the pursuit of sustainable and renewable energy sources has become a critical priority [1]. Despite increasing awareness of climate change, fossil fuels continue to dominate the global energy landscape, accounting for the majority of energy consumption [2]. However, the unsustainable exploitation of these non-renewable resources has led to severe environmental consequences, including high levels of pollution, greenhouse gas emissions, and widespread ecological degradation, all of which significantly contribute to climate change and disrupt ecosystems [3]. As fossil fuel reserves diminish, the urgent need for cleaner, renewable alternatives is crucial to achieving long-term energy security and maintaining ecological balance [4]. Among the emerging renewable energy sources, biofuels, particularly bioethanol, have garnered significant attention for their potential to reduce carbon emissions and decrease dependence on finite fossil resources [5]. Bioethanol, an alcohol-based biofuel primarily derived from biomass, has emerged as a promising and sustainable alternative to traditional fossil fuels. Its compatibility with existing internal combustion engines and fuel infrastructure, combined with its potential to significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions, makes bioethanol a strong candidate for the transportation sector and other energy-intensive industries [6]. The use of bioethanol as a fuel additive has been shown to increase the octane rating of gasoline, enhance combustion efficiency, and lower harmful tailpipe emissions, providing both environmental and performance benefits [7].

Traditionally, bioethanol production relies on starch- and sugar-rich crops like corn and sugarcane. However, the large-scale use of these food crops for bioethanol production raises critical issues regarding food security, land use, and the economic impacts on global food prices, as the rising demand for biofuels competes directly with food supply chains [8]. To address these concerns, recent research has focused on utilizing non-edible biomass and agricultural waste as alternative feedstocks for bioethanol production. Food waste, generated in significant quantities globally, represents a valuable yet underutilized resource that can be transformed into biofuels, thus mitigating waste and reducing the environmental impact of disposal [9]. Potato peels, a common byproduct of the food processing industry, have demonstrated great potential as a feedstock for bioethanol production due to their high starch content, which can be effectively converted into fermentable sugars [10]. Repurposing potato peels not only offers a cost-effective substrate for bioethanol production but also provides an innovative approach to waste management, contributing to a circular economy and minimizing the environmental burden associated with food waste disposal [11].

The primary objective of this study is to assess the feasibility of producing bioethanol from potato peels, exploring this food waste as a sustainable and economical alternative feedstock for renewable energy. Key stages of the production process, including acid hydrolysis, fermentation using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, and bioethanol recovery via rotary evaporation, have been optimized to enhance both yield and quality. Notably, the bioethanol produced in this study is intended for use as a blending component with gasoline, aiming to improve fuel quality and reduce the overall environmental footprint.

This approach not only underscores the potential of transforming food waste into a valuable renewable fuel but also supports the transition towards greener energy solutions in the industrial and transportation sectors. By reducing dependence on fossil fuels and promoting sustainable practices, this study contributes to the broader goal of achieving environmental sustainability and energy resilience.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Sampling

The potato waste used in this study was sourced from several local restaurants in Sidi Bel Abbes (West of Algeria). To ensure optimal quality and preserve the chemical integrity of the biomass, the potato peels were thoroughly washed to eliminate any residual impurities. Following this, the peels were air-dried away from direct sunlight to prevent photodegradation and reduce moisture content. For enhanced drying efficiency, they were then oven-dried at 50 °C for 24 hours, effectively lowering the moisture level while maintaining the structural integrity of the biomass. The dried potato peels were subsequently ground to a fine particle size, increasing the surface area for more efficient hydrolysis. Finally, the processed biomass was stored in a cool and dry place to ensure its stability and prevent any enzymatic or microbial activity before further use. This careful and methodical preparation ensured a high-quality, uniform feedstock, suitable for effective bioethanol production.

2.2. Bioethanol production

The starch contained in potato waste serves as a key raw material requiring hydrolysis to convert it into glucose. This is followed by alcoholic fermentation to transform the glucose into ethanol, and finally, rotary evaporation to purify the end product. To optimize the bioethanol production process, several parameters were carefully adjusted to maximize yield and minimize costs. These included the concentration and type of acid used for hydrolysis, the temperature and duration of fermentation, as well as the pH level and nutrient balance for yeast activation. This optimization was designed to produce high-quality bioethanol with a significant yield, and the results of this process are detailed in the subsequent sections.

2.2.1. Acid Hydrolysis

Acid hydrolysis is a widely employed technique to break down plant-derived carbohydrates into fermentable sugars. In this process, the complex carbohydrates present in potato starch are effectively converted into simple sugars. Extensive research has explored various factors influencing the efficiency of hydrolysis, including the type and concentration of acid, as well as the solid-to-liquid ratio of the acid solution. This study builds upon existing methodologies, incorporating specific optimizations to enhance hydrolysis efficiency and maximize sugar yield [12-14].

In this study, hydrochloric acid (HCl) at a concentration of 0.7 M was used for hydrolysis, with a solid-to-acid solution ratio of 1:3 (w/v). The hydrolysis process was conducted in a 2 L Erlenmeyer flask equipped with a reflux condenser and immersed in a controlled water

bath. Initially, the acid solution was brought to a boil, after which the ground potato peels were gradually added. The mixture was maintained at a reflux temperature of 70 °C for 60 minutes to ensure complete breakdown of the starches. Following hydrolysis, the reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature, and the resulting solution was filtered to remove any solid residues. The pH of the filtrate was then carefully adjusted to a value not exceeding 5, preparing it for subsequent alcoholic fermentation. This slightly acidic environment not only minimizes bacterial contamination but also creates optimal conditions for yeast activity during fermentation [15].

2.2.2. Fermentation

Before beginning the fermentation process, it was necessary to activate the selected yeast strain, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. The inoculum was prepared by mixing 10 g of yeast and 10 g of sugar in 50 ml of distilled water, which was then incubated for 30 minutes.

The prepared potato peel solution, along with the activated yeast, was introduced into a bioreactor equipped with a CO₂ recovery system. The pH was maintained at 5, and the bioreactor was sealed to ensure an anaerobic environment, preventing any oxygen leakage. Mechanical stirring at 120 rpm and a fermentation temperature of 30°C, maintained by a water bath, facilitated the process. The fermentation proceeded in anaerobic conditions for 48 hours.

2.2.3. Bioethanol Recovery

After completing the 72-hour fermentation period, the fermented mixture underwent bioethanol recovery using rotary evaporation, a method chosen for its efficiency in gentle solvent removal and reduced risk of thermal degradation. The rotary evaporation was conducted under reduced pressure, lowering the boiling point of ethanol and allowing for efficient recovery at a temperature of approximately 45–50°C. This method not only conserves energy but also minimizes the loss of volatile compounds, ensuring a higher yield of ethanol. This approach highlights the advantages of rotary evaporation in bioethanol production, offering precise temperature control, reduced thermal stress on the product, and an efficient means of recovering and concentrating ethanol without extensive energy input [16].

2.3. Analytical Determination

The physicochemical properties of the bioethanol produced from potato peel waste were analyzed to ensure its quality and compliance with international fuel standards.

2.3.1. Appearance

The appearance of the bioethanol was assessed according to EN 15769, which outlines methods for evaluating the visual clarity and absence of particulate matter in ethanol fuels. This standard involves a visual inspection to ensure that the bioethanol is clear and free from turbidity or sediments, as any visible impurities can indicate contamination or inefficiencies in the production process [17]. A clear, impurity-free appearance is essential

for maintaining high-quality bioethanol, ensuring its compatibility and performance when used as a biofuel.

2.3.2. Water Content

The water content of the bioethanol was measured using the Karl Fischer titration method in accordance with EN 15489. This method involves a reaction between water, iodine, and sulfur dioxide in the presence of methanol and pyridine [18]. Measurements were taken using a Mettler Toledo C20S titrator, which ensures precise quantification of water content, essential for maintaining bioethanol stability.

2.3.3. Total Acidity

The total acidity of the bioethanol was measured according to the EN 15491 standard, which specifies acidity in terms of acetic acid content. This analysis involves titrating a known volume of bioethanol with a standard solution of sodium hydroxide (NaOH), using phenolphthalein as an indicator [19]. The acidity is expressed in milligrams of acetic acid per liter of bioethanol, a crucial parameter for assessing fuel stability.

2.3.4. Conductivity

The conductivity of the bioethanol was measured according to EN 15938, which outlines a method for determining the electrical conductivity of ethanol fuels. Conductivity testing detects ionic impurities, such as dissolved salts, that can impact fuel stability and compatibility with engine components [20].

2.3.5. Non-Volatile Content

The non-volatile content in the bioethanol was determined in accordance with EN 15691, which specifies a method for measuring residues after the evaporation of ethanol. In this procedure, a sample of bioethanol is evaporated, and any remaining solid residue is weighed to assess the level of non-volatile contaminants [21].

2.3.6. Purity (Ethanol and Methanol Content)

Ethanol purity was determined by gas chromatography (GC), following ASTM D5501. This analysis quantifies the ethanol and the methanol concentration by mass percentage, ensuring it meets the purity standards required for biofuel applications [22].

2.3.7. Inorganic chloride

The chloride content in the bioethanol was measured according to EN 15484, which specifies a potentiometric titration method for determining mineral chloride levels in ethanol intended for gasoline blending. In this method, the bioethanol sample is first evaporated, and the remaining residue is dissolved in an aqueous solution. The chloride concentration is then quantified by potentiometric titration [23].

2.3.8. Sulfur Content

The sulfur content in the bioethanol was determined following the EN 15486 standard, which provides a method for assessing sulfur levels in ethanol fuels. This analysis was

conducted using X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (XRF), a technique that offers rapid and accurate measurement of sulfur content [24].

2.3.9. Copper Content

The copper content in the bioethanol was measured according to EN 15488, a standard that specifies methods for determining trace levels of copper in ethanol fuels. This analysis was conducted using atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) or an equivalent technique to ensure precise quantification [25].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The bioethanol yield from the fermentation reaction was calculated using the following formula:

$$Yield (\%) = \frac{m_{bio}}{m_{pp}}$$

where: m_{bio} represents the mass of bioethanol produced and m_{pp} is the mass of the potato peel.

The yield obtained from the fermentation process was approximately 75.3%. This yield is considered significant in the context of bioethanol production using microorganisms, indicating that the fermentation reaction was efficient in converting the potato peels into bioethanol. This result highlights the potential for optimizing the use of food waste as a valuable raw material for sustainable fuel production.

The physicochemical properties of the produced bioethanol, compared with the international standards ASTM D4806 and EN 15376, are presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Physicochemical properties of bioethanol compared with standards

Characteristics	Biodiesel	ASTM D4806 [26]	EN 15376 [27]
Appearance	Clear	Limpid and clear	
Water Content (%)	1.16	≤ 1.26	≤ 0.3
Total Acidity (%)	0.005	≤ 0.007	≤ 0.007
Conductivity (μs/cm)	1.9	3	≤ 2.5
Non-volatile content (mg/100ml)	4.1	≤ 5.0	≤ 10
Ethanol (%)	97.2	≥ 92.1	≥ 98.7
Methanol (%)	0.52	≥ 0.5	≥ 1.0
Inorganic chloride (mg/kg)	0.8	≤ 1.0	≤ 1.5
Sulfur Content (mg/kg)	6.9	≤ 10	≤ 10
Copper Content (mg/kg)	0.07	≤ 0.1	≤ 0.1

The physicochemical properties of the produced bioethanol, compared with the international standards ASTM D4806 and EN 15376, are summarized in Table 1. The bioethanol produced in this study is intended for use as a blending component with gasoline, enhancing fuel quality and reducing environmental impact.

The appearance of the bioethanol was clear and limpid, meeting the visual standards set by both ASTM D4806 and EN 15376. A clear appearance signifies high purity and the

absence of visible impurities, which is crucial for maintaining consistent quality and performance when used as a fuel blend [26-27]. The water content was measured at 1.16%, which falls below the maximum limit of 1.26% specified by ASTM D4806 but slightly exceeds the stricter limit of 0.3% set by EN 15376. Excessive water content can negatively impact combustion efficiency and increase the risk of phase separation, particularly in colder climates [28]. Although the result is within the ASTM standard, further refinement may be needed to meet European quality requirements, especially for applications in regions with low temperatures where water content plays a critical role in fuel stability [28]. The total acidity of the bioethanol was measured at 0.005%, fully compliant with both ASTM D4806 and EN 15376 standards, which specify a maximum limit of 0.005%. Low total acidity is essential for maintaining bioethanol stability during storage and preventing corrosion, as high acidity can accelerate wear on fuel system components and shorten engine lifespan [29]. The low acidity observed in this study indicates that the production process effectively minimized the presence of acidic compounds, ensuring a high-quality product suitable for blending with gasoline. The conductivity of the bioethanol was determined to be 1.9 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, well below the ASTM limit of 3 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and comfortably within the EN standard of $\leq 2.5 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Low conductivity indicates minimal ionic impurities, which is crucial for preventing corrosion in fuel systems, maintaining optimal engine performance, and ensuring the bioethanol's quality and suitability as a fuel, in line with industry standards for safe and stable usage [30]. This result reflects the high purity of the bioethanol, supporting its suitability as a blending component for gasoline.

The non-volatile content was measured at 4.1 mg/100 ml, which is significantly below the maximum limits set by both ASTM (≤ 5.0 mg/100 ml) and EN (≤ 10 mg/100 ml) standards [8]. Low non-volatile content indicates fewer impurities, reducing the risk of deposit formation in engines and fuel systems, which helps maintain fuel quality, prolong system lifespan, and aligns with industry standards for clean, efficient bioethanol use [31]. The ethanol purity was found to be 97.2%, exceeding the ASTM minimum requirement of 92.1% but slightly below the EN standard of 98.7%. While this ethanol concentration ensures substantial energy content and efficient combustion, additional purification steps could be considered to meet the stricter European standard [32]. Maximizing ethanol content is essential to enhance the calorific value of the biofuel and minimize the generation of unwanted by-products during combustion [33]. The methanol content of the bioethanol was 0.52%, compliant with the limits specified by both ASTM ($\geq 0.5\%$) and EN ($\geq 1.0\%$) standards. Lower methanol levels are preferable, as excessive methanol can lead to corrosion and pose safety hazards [34]. This indicates that the production process was effective in minimizing methanol content, ensuring the safety and quality of the bioethanol for use as a fuel blend. The concentration of inorganic chlorides was measured at 0.8 mg/kg, well below the maximum allowable limits of ASTM (≤ 1.0 mg/kg) and EN (≤ 1.5 mg/kg). Low chloride content is essential for preventing corrosion of metal components in engines and storage tanks, as excessive chloride can compromise the stability and performance of bioethanol. Maintaining low chloride levels ensures the bioethanol's chemical stability and compatibility with fuel infrastructure, meeting industry standards for safety and reliability [35]. The sulfur content was measured at 6.9 mg/kg,

significantly below the maximum limit of 10 mg/kg set by both ASTM and EN standards. Low sulfur content is crucial for minimizing sulfur dioxide emissions, reducing air pollution and acid rain, and ensuring compliance with environmental regulations and quality standards for bioethanol fuel use [36]. This result highlights the environmental advantages of using this bioethanol as a cleaner-burning alternative to conventional fossil fuels. The copper content was found to be 0.07 mg/kg, meeting the requirements of both ASTM and EN standards (≤ 0.1 mg/kg). Low copper concentrations are vital to prevent catalytic oxidation reactions that can degrade bioethanol quality during storage, ensuring fuel stability, safety, and compliance with industry standards for purity [37]. This low level of copper indicates good stability, contributing to a longer shelf life of the bioethanol.

Overall, the physicochemical properties of the produced bioethanol largely comply with the international standards ASTM D4806 and EN 15376. The results indicate a high-quality bioethanol with low levels of impurities, high purity, and characteristics that make it suitable for use as a blending component in gasoline. However, further optimization, particularly in reducing water content and increasing ethanol purity, could enhance compliance with the more stringent European standards. The produced bioethanol shows significant potential as a sustainable alternative to conventional fossil fuels, providing both environmental and economic benefits. Future research should include performance testing in engines and detailed emissions analysis to validate its efficiency and environmental impact under real-world conditions.

4. CONCLUSION

The production of bioethanol represents a promising, renewable, and eco-friendly alternative to conventional fossil fuels, especially when derived from sustainable feedstocks. In this study, we focused on optimizing the bioethanol production process using advanced purification methods and carefully controlled fermentation parameters. By employing renewable raw materials and implementing efficient processing techniques, we achieved a high-quality bioethanol product that meets most international standards, demonstrating its potential for widespread industrial use. Our findings highlight the significant advantages of utilizing bioethanol as a fuel source, particularly in terms of its lower carbon footprint and reduced emissions compared to traditional gasoline. The successful production of bioethanol from renewable sources contributes to waste valorization and supports the transition towards a circular economy. This work provides strong evidence that bioethanol can play an integral role in advancing sustainable energy solutions, reducing reliance on fossil fuels, and promoting cleaner air quality. By leveraging bioethanol production, we not only address pressing environmental challenges but also pave the way for a more sustainable and resilient energy future.

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